

A SHORT PRESENTATION OF VOLUME MATERIALS

Sadeq Ali Saad Al Yaari and Nassr Almaflehi propose an interesting study which deals with the measuring of the validity and reliability of ABR (Auditory Brainstem Responses) through screening, estimating, and intraoperative monitoring auditory capabilities of Arab infants and children and the degree of their seriousness.

The research of Gergana Atanassova Petkova deals with 24 Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names Latin by origin, canonized by the Orthodox Church.

Voudina Ngarsou analyzes from sociolinguistic and cultural points of view the spoken French in 5 Tchad towns.

The majority of children's books are written by adults, thus, they inevitably show the image adults have in their mind about children/childhood or how children should be like. Cătălina Bălinișteanu's paper reveals the adult's wish to educate, manipulate or instruct children through these books. Consequently, the author analyses how these narratives increase the children's agency and their self-awareness in a manner that subverts the adults' authority.

In Victorian male fiction hair occurs as a recurrent synecdoche, as a part of the object which represented female sexuality. By a semiotic approach to images of female hair in Charles Dickens's novel "Dombey and Son", Ioana Boghian's paper aims at identifying the way in which women's hair representations functioned as indicators for the (de)stabilization of patriarchal power in the Victorian age.

Lyubov Kit's article deals with the notion of intimacy from a linguistic point of view. Frame analysis helped to establish the categorization of types and nominators of intimate speech genres, their construction in static and dynamic aspects.

Mihaela Culea explores the ways in which English writer Sue Townsend, in "The Queen and I" (1992), mirrors the socio-economic concerns of the British population, especially related to the differing lives of two social groups placed at opposite poles of the social hierarchy.

Luiza Șosu explores the artistic detail value in a text applying E. Coseriu's theory and V. Kuharenco's practical classification.

Anna Dzyubenko proposes a shot pragmalinguistic interpretation of the modern British female fiction.